

Translation of Linguo-Cultural Vocabulary Layer: Cultural Distance, Loss of Nuance, Intertextuality

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ABSTRACT

The translation of linguo-cultural vocabulary in literary texts is a complex and multifaceted process, influenced by both linguistic and cultural elements inherent in the source and target languages. This article examines the specific features and methods involved in translating cultural terms and expressions, often referred to as the linguo-cultural layer. By exploring the impact of cultural differences, the role of context, and translation strategies, this paper aims to provide a comprehensive understanding of how translators navigate the challenges of rendering culturally significant vocabulary while preserving meaning, tone, and aesthetic qualities in literary works.

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Lingvomadaniy lug‘at qatlamini tarjimasi: madaniy masofa, nuansining yo‘qolishi, intertekstuallik

Keywords:

tarjima, lingvomadaniy lug‘at,
madaniy moslashuv,
transliteratsiya, madaniy
o‘rinbosarlik, tarjima
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ANNOTATSIYA

Badiiy matnlardagi lingvomadaniy lug‘atning tarjimasi murakkab va ko‘p qirrali jarayon bo‘lib, manba va ko‘chma tillarga xos bo‘lgan ham lingvistik, ham madaniy elementlar ta‘sirida namoyon bo‘ladi. Ushbu maqolada ko‘pincha lingvo-madaniy qatlam deb ataladigan madaniy atama va iboralarni tarjima qilishning o‘ziga xos xususiyatlari va usullari ko‘rib chiqiladi. Madaniy tafovutlar, kontekstning

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roli va tarjima strategiyalarining taʼsirini oʻrganib, ushbu maqola adabiy asarlarda maʼno, ohang va estetik fazilatlarni saqlab qolgan holda tarjimonlar madaniy ahamiyatga ega lugʼatni koʻrsatish muammolarini qanday hal qilishlari haqida keng qamrovli tushuncha berishga qaratilgan.

Перевод лингвокультурного лексического слоя: культурная дистанция, потеря нюансов, интертекстуальность

Keywords:

перевод, лингвокультурный словарь, культурная адаптация, транслитерация, культурная замена, стратегии перевода, интертекстуальность.

АННОТАЦИЯ

Перевод лингвокультурного слоя лексики в литературных текстах – сложный и многогранный процесс, на который влияют как лингвистические, так и культурные элементы, присущие исходному и целевому языкам. В данной статье рассматриваются специфика и методы, задействованные при переводе культурных терминов и выражений, часто называемых лингвокультурным слоем. Изучая влияние культурных различий, роль контекста и стратегии перевода, данная статья направлена на обеспечение всестороннего понимания того, как переводчики справляются с трудностями передачи культурно значимой лексики, сохраняя при этом значение, тон и эстетические качества в литературных произведениях.

INTRODUCTION

Literary translation is a unique branch of translation studies, characterized by its focus on the transfer of not just words, but the subtleties, emotions, and cultural context of the original text [1]. One of the most challenging aspects of translating literary works is the rendering of linguo-cultural vocabulary, a layer of language rich with cultural connotations, historical references, idiomatic expressions, and socially embedded meanings [2; 4]. This layer often includes terms, phrases, or expressions that do not have direct equivalents in the target language [12], making the translation process intricate and demanding.

The linguo-cultural vocabulary layer includes a wide range of elements, such as customs, traditions, place names, food items, folklore, social institutions, religious references, and historical events [3]. These terms serve as a bridge to the culture of the source text [14] but may pose significant difficulties in translation [6]. This paper investigates the specific features of linguo-cultural vocabulary and explores the methods employed by translators to effectively convey these elements across languages and cultures.

RESULTS. SPECIFIC FEATURES OF LINGUO-CULTURAL VOCABULARY

Linguo-cultural vocabulary represents a unique fusion of language and culture. This vocabulary can be categorized into the following types:

- ✓ **Cultural Realia:** These are words that refer to specific cultural objects, practices, or phenomena, such as "piñata" in Spanish or "sauna" in Finnish [13]. These terms often do not have direct equivalents in other languages [16], requiring the translator to either retain the original term, adapt it, or provide an explanation.
- ✓ **Social Institutions:** Concepts like legal systems, governmental structures, and educational institutions may carry cultural weight, such as the word "duuma" (the Russian legislative body) or "parliament" in a different political context [5].
- ✓ **Customs and Traditions:** These terms reflect cultural practices and holidays, such as "Thanksgiving" or "Diwali." Translating these terms involves understanding the cultural significance behind them and adapting it for the target audience [7].
- ✓ **Idiomatic Expressions and Proverbs:** Idioms or proverbs are deeply rooted in culture and may require significant adaptation or substitution in translation. For instance, the Russian expression "не всё коту масленица" ("it's not always "Pancake Week for the cat") may require an entirely different expression in English that conveys a similar meaning, such as "it's not always sunny." [8]
- ✓ **Food and Cuisine:** Food names can serve as cultural markers, such as "sushi" in Japanese or "borsch" in Russian [9]. These terms are sometimes untranslatable or require a cultural note to clarify their significance.

These categories illustrate the broad scope of linguo-cultural vocabulary in literary texts, which often challenge the translator's ability to maintain both the integrity of the original and the cultural relevance of the target language.

METHODS OF TRANSLATION

Translating linguo-cultural vocabulary requires a range of strategies, each depending on the nature of the term, the text's genre, and the translator's approach to fidelity and creativity. The following are some common methods used:

1. Transliteration

Transliteration is the process of transferring a term directly from the source language to the target language, often used for names, places, or culturally unique items [11]. For instance, the term "Sushi" in Japanese might be transliterated directly into English, as it is a globally recognized concept. While transliteration helps retain the cultural flavor, it may also require the addition of a brief explanation for clarity, particularly in the case of lesser-known terms.

2. Loanwords and Borrowings

Sometimes, cultural terms are borrowed directly from the source language and incorporated into the target language with minimal alteration. For example, "karma" in English, originating from Sanskrit, is widely used in Western cultures without significant modification. This method works best when the target culture has adopted the foreign concept, making it familiar to the reader.

3. Cultural Substitution

Cultural substitution involves replacing a term or concept from the source language with one that carries a similar meaning or cultural resonance in the target language. For example, "Thanksgiving" might be substituted with "Christmas" or "Easter" in certain cases if these holidays have more significance in the target culture [10; 16]. This method ensures that the reader can connect with the translated text on a cultural level.

4. Descriptive Translation or Explanation

When a term has no direct equivalent in the target language, it may be necessary to describe it. This method involves providing an explanation or a footnote to ensure the reader understands the term. For instance, the term "sauna" might be accompanied by a brief description of its cultural context and usage, such as "a traditional Finnish steam bath."

5. Calque or Loan Translation

Calque involves translating the component parts of a foreign term literally into the target language. For example, the French term "gratte-ciel" (literally "scrape-sky") is translated into English as "skyscraper." This method works well when the foreign term can be broken down into easily understandable parts that make sense in the target language.

6. Omission

In some cases, if a culturally specific term does not significantly affect the text's meaning or if it would be too cumbersome to explain, the translator may choose to omit it entirely. This strategy is often used for minor details, but it should be employed carefully to avoid losing the cultural texture of the original.

7. Compensation

In compensation, the translator might omit certain cultural details in one part of the text but introduce them elsewhere to maintain the overall balance of cultural richness [15]. For example, if a specific cultural reference in one passage is untranslatable, the translator may compensate by adding a reference elsewhere in the text that evokes a similar cultural context.

DISCUSSION. CHALLENGES IN TRANSLATING LINGUO-CULTURAL VOCABULARY

The translation of linguo-cultural vocabulary is fraught with challenges due to several factors:

- ✓ **Cultural Distance:** The greater the cultural distance between the source and target languages, the more difficult it becomes to preserve the original meaning. For instance, translating Russian folklore references into English may result in the loss of cultural nuances that are familiar to Russian readers but obscure to English-speaking audiences.
- ✓ **Loss of Nuance:** Certain cultural terms may carry emotional, historical, or ideological weight that is difficult to convey in translation. A simple term like "democracy" might hold different connotations in different cultures, influenced by political history and social context.

- ✓ Intertextuality: In literary texts, words often take on additional meaning through intertextual references to other works, historical events, or cultural traditions. Translating such layered terms requires a deep understanding of both the source and target cultures.

CONCLUSION

The translation of linguo-cultural vocabulary in literary texts is a process that requires more than just linguistic skill; it demands cultural sensitivity, creativity, and an understanding of the target audience. The methods used to translate these terms—whether through direct transliteration, substitution, or descriptive elaboration—must take into account the complexities of both languages and their respective cultures. Translators must balance accuracy with cultural adaptation, ensuring that the essence of the original text is conveyed without losing the rich cultural context that defines it.

As globalization continues to intertwine cultures, the demand for effective translation of linguo-cultural vocabulary is likely to grow. Understanding the nuances of cultural transfer and refining the methods used to translate these terms will remain an essential aspect of literary translation, enriching the cross-cultural dialogue that translation facilitates.

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